

Special Relativity and Translational Invariance Yielding the Wavelength/Period as a Intervals

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Special relativity involves the Lorentz transformation matrix which contains velocity v , and acts on 4-vectors. (p,E) and (x,t) are two common examples. Interestingly, we argue, v , p and E are invariant under spatial and time translations, but x and t are not. An interval in time (time period) and interval in space (wavelength), however, are spatially invariant. Thus we argue that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ should give rise to time and spatial intervals in order to have overall translation (time and space) invariance. This leads to temporal and spatial intervals linked with specific E and p values, because x and t are not intervals by themselves. The time interval is \hbar/E and the spatial \hbar/p . By defining these intervals at an E , p level, interactions with intervals existing in nature, e.g. a 2-slit interval, are associated with a wavelength which in turn is dependent on p through \hbar/p . Thus p does not simply represent an impulse, but is linked with a spatial type of probability $\exp(ipx)$. This idea carries over into the Newtonian picture because one may take the nonrelativistic limit of $A = -Et + px$, namely $-Et + px$ for a free particle with $E = p^2/2m$ and $p = mv$. This quantity, however, is not a naturally occurring one in Newton's theory and so the issue of a lack of translational invariance in x and t is not apparent.

Quantum Free Particle and Quantum Mechanics

We have argued in previous notes that the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((1))$$

yields free particle quantum mechanics because if $t \rightarrow t + \hbar/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \hbar/p$, A remains unchanged. Thus there is an uncertainty associated with x and t . This uncertainty is specifically associated with translational behaviour in space and time. x and t are measured by a ruler and clock and may be shifted. Thus they don't have an absolute physical value even though they appear in a 4-vector.

Such is not the case for $v = dx/dt$, $E = m\gamma c^2$ and $p = m\gamma v$. These are not affected by translations in space and time. As a result, we argue that this is an issue for ((10)) because it contains t and x which may be shifted. As noted previously,

$$T \rightarrow T + \hbar/E \quad \text{and} \quad x \rightarrow x + \hbar/p \quad ((2))$$

leave A ((1)) unchanged. One may argue for the existence of x and t uncertainty which is periodic with \hbar/E being the time length (period) and \hbar/p the space length (wavelength). More specifically, one may write eigenfunctions of the translation generators:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt) \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad -i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((3b))$$

Physical Consequences

We argue that because x and t are not invariant under translations, while v, p, E are, an invariance must be created internally. Thus one should look for a Lorentz invariant which contains t, x as well as measuring measurable such as p which represents impulse. This suggests impulse, which in Newtonian mechanics, may be measured by “damage” to a target, must now help to define an x interval. Similarly, E may help define a time period. In this manner, x and t become wavelength and time period and are invariant under spatial and time translations. This has consequences because it means each E and p define a different time period and wavelength. The notion of spatial interval and time period do not exist a priori in the Lorentz invariant ((1)). They must be created.

This creation of a time period and wavelength based on E and p has physical consequences. P is no longer only measured by the damage it may do to a target, but also by its spatial interval i.e. the wavelength \hbar/p . Different p 's have different wavelengths associated with a kind of probability $\exp(ipx)$. One sees effects when there exist objects in space representing the same length interval. For example, a two-slit apparatus with slit spacing of \hbar/p “picks” out or creates an interference pattern for a momentum of p . A very small p with a large wavelength would not be sensitive to this particular 2-slit apparatus.

Thus it is the creation of time and spatial intervals directly from $-Et+px$ which gives rise to the quantum behaviour of time periods (or the reciprocal frequency) and wavelengths, we argue.

Newtonian Mechanics

Why don't these considerations occur in Newtonian mechanics? Velocity, E and p for a free particle are translationally invariant and x and t are not. Consider an invariant containing p and x , i.e.

$$pp/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

E is translationally invariant, but because one follows a particle at x at t and this problem contains acceleration:

$$p(x) \text{ is not equal to } p(x+a) \text{ and } V(x) \text{ not equal } V(x+a) \quad ((5))$$

The shifts in values $pp/2m$ and $V(x)$, however, compensate for each other without any need to create a wavelength.

In the case of a free Newtonian particle:

$$E = pp/2m \quad ((6))$$

There is no x or t in this equation so p does not create a wavelength spatial interval. For the constant v equation:

$$x = vt \quad ((7))$$

X and t are not spatially invariant, but $x=vt$ holds assuming $t=0$ when $x=0$. The formal equation is:

$$dx/dt = v \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is translationally invariant. As a result, it seems one does not have x, t commonly appear in an invariant equation containing translationally invariant quantities like v or constant p, E . As a result, one may be under the impression that there is no concept of a time period associated with E or wavelength associated with p .

Consider, however, $A = -Et + px = -m_0 t_0$ where t_0 is time in a rest frame. Taking the nonrelativistic limit yields:

$$-m_0 t_0 = -m_0 t - p_0 x / 2m_0 + p_0 x \quad ((9)) \quad (\text{Here } p_0 = m_0 v.) \quad (\text{free particle})$$

((9)) contains x, t which are translationally noninvariant as well as nonrelativistic energy $p_0^2/2m_0$ and momentum p_0 which are translationally invariant. m_0 is a constant and so one may have nonrelativistic fluctuations $t \rightarrow t + \hbar / (p_0^2/2m_0)$ and $x \rightarrow x + \hbar / p_0$. Thus the notion of quantum time period and wavelength should also hold in nonrelativistic physics as they do in the Schrodinger equation.

The last two terms in ((9)) hold in Newtonian mechanics through:

$$(-Et + px)/t \text{ with } x/t=v \rightarrow -E + pv = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = E \quad ((10))$$

It just seems that one would never write $-Et+px$ in Newtonian mechanics as it is not a natural invariant in the theory and so would not try to have E and p create time and spatial invariants.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued in a number of previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics, namely time period (1/frequency) and wavelength, follow from the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$ where $t \rightarrow t + \hbar/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \hbar/p$ leave A unchanged. Thus, time and spatial fluctuations acting in a periodic manner (i.e. time periods and wavelengths) leave A unchanged. From there, we created eigenfunctions of the translation generators $i\hbar/dt$ and $-i\hbar/dx$ to obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$.

Here we argue that the central issue seems to be the fact that velocity $v=dx/dt$, $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ are invariant under translations of t and x , but x and t themselves are not. As a result, there seems to be an issue with the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ because E, p are translationally invariant, but x and t are not. We argue that x and t may become associated with translationally invariant quantities by becoming intervals. They, however, do not exist as intervals a priori, so E and p in $A = -Et+px$ are needed to convert them. This leads to the idea that time and spatial intervals are defined internally by E and p with \hbar/E being the time interval and \hbar/p the spatial i.e. wavelength. P is associated with impulses in Newtonian physics. Now it also creates a wavelength of the order \hbar/p which is

associated with a probability $\exp(ipx)$. Thus even though the impulse p exists at each p , there are different probabilities to be at x given by $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, this interval based physics (created by p because x is a priori not translationally invariant) should manifest itself in an interaction with another interval the same size i.e. a two slit apparatus with the slits being about \hbar/p apart. This is seen experimentally.